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**CHILDREN'S INFLUENCE ON PURCHASE DECISIONS IN
HOUSEHOLDS: A LITERATURE REVIEW AND
BIBLIOMETRIC ANALYSIS.**

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FOR XIME JOURNAL ISSUE 3 2022

Abstract

Background: The present study attempts to bring together the observations and findings of research studies related to children's influence on household purchase decisions.

Methods: Research literature from 2001 to 2021 was analyzed to examine past research on children's impacts on purchasing decisions using the software VOSviewer. The objective is to highlight some of the associated strengths and limitations that define this field of research and suggest some potential future research directions. This section offers facts regarding the number of noteworthy research papers, journal information, indexed author keywords related to the domain, a country-wise citation index, and author-specific citations.

Results: According to the findings of the study, bibliometric analysis is critical in delving into the theoretical literature and establishing an integrated theoretical framework on the quality of children's influence in households. In addition to summarizing and evaluating the subject matter, this paper helps identify the gaps in the existing body of literature.

Keywords

Bibliometric Analysis, Consumer Behaviour, Family, Pester Power, Purchase Decisions.

Introduction

Children as customers or influences of family purchasing have been extensively explored and studied in the marketing literature (Kaur 2006). They were traditionally described as adorable, innocent, and pleasant. The term "consumer" was never connected with children. The globe has changed socially and economically during the last few decades. The proliferation of the internet has shrunk the planet.

All of the technical, social, and economic developments have enhanced the influence of children on family purchasing decisions. Children were self-reliant and active from their early childhoods due to the ease with which knowledge was available and their parents' busy schedules, and increasing discretionary cash. Their childhood innocence has been supplanted by commercialized connections with their parents (Mc Neal, 1964). As a result, children's purchasing power has risen substantially over time, according to a Nickelodeon (2013) study, and family decision-making has become more collaborative.

Many times, the impact of children on family purchase decisions has been highlighted and publicly acknowledged. (Kerrane et al., 2012; Tomko, 2012). However, previous research has focused on advertising and television media as the primary sources of pester power (Gulla & Purohit 2013). The product category, the child's age, and the family communication pattern all have a significant impact on pester power (Ahuja and Stinson, 1993, Haynes et al., 1993; Ozgen, 2003). Marketing firms frequently use pester power to target parents. Children have little discretionary income and, as a result, are unable to purchase items for themselves and look to their parents to buy for them their desired products (Chaudhary, Monica 2012).

According to Sharma and Sonwaney (2013), the style of family communication, family demographics, media, peers, and the child's demographic profile such as age, gender, and the number of siblings, all have an essential role in the degree of exerting authority or nagging the

parents for a specific product (Marshall 2007). These antecedents have a direct or indirect impact on the family's purchasing decisions.

Literature Review

This article refers to nearly 120 studies published between 2001 and 2021. The publications are split into four key phases that significantly highlight a particular factor influencing children. These categories help in understanding the significant influencers during the specified years.

Teletubbies, Talking, and Television [2001-2005]

This stage focused on the influence of television on children's decisions. Research articles clearly show that word of mouth is a preferred method of communication among tweens. Colors and cartoon figures and characters were employed in advertisements to capture the interest of young viewers, who were the focus of the studies. Children's retail shopping experiences were also investigated in terms of their interactions with parents. Authors from India began to recognize the presence of pester power in households.

Pester power, according to Pilgrim (2001), is a destructive idea. In his study, Pilgrim emphasized the importance of brand awareness among young children at an early age. He claims that this is due to marketers' developing advertising that exploits children's innocence. According to De Chencey (2001), Hip Culture is becoming increasingly popular among children. Therefore, the majority of the advertising market will be dominated by children solely. Bergstrom's (2001) paper discussed numerous ways of attracting youngsters to a business. According to Procter (2002), the most common mode of communication among youngsters is word-of-mouth.

Dammeler's (2003) study was an empirical study in which the author employed varied colours and fonts in advertisements to target different age groups. According to the responses collected,

younger children were more drawn to visuals than older children. Coughlin's 2003 study focused on children's behaviour in retail outlets. He linked cameras to youngsters and recorded the stuff they enjoyed the most. He investigated new aspects of in-store marketing.

Geraci's study from 2004 emphasised the need for ethical procedures while creating advertisements for youngsters. The commercials aimed towards youngsters are unhealthy and nutritionally deficient. He advised parents to tell their children about the ingredients in any food items.

According to Spungin (2004), the literacy level of parents plays a critical role in mitigating the negative consequences of pester power in parent-child relationships. Parents believe that advertisers exploit children's innocence for profit. Mc Dougal's (2004) study investigated youths' relationships with companies that tried to link them for a more extended period.

According to Moses (2005), advertising will continue to exist alongside children's lives. However, few companies will become their favourites, leaving a lasting impression on their impressionable minds. Chadva (2005) emphasises the effect of children on their parents while purchasing things in various areas. Kurnit (2005) suggests that marketers advertise responsibly. The paper further explains the impact of television on kids.

Fun, Freebies, and Fashion [2006- 2010]

This phase emphasised multi-country investigations that discovered identical traits among youngsters that used pester power. According to researchers' fashion has an impact on youngsters under the age of ten. Several studies have found a downward trend in TV viewership as youngsters have begun to access the internet. During this period, scholars questioned the ethical standards of marketing to minors. Also, a few studies have investigated the effectiveness of premiums and freebies with products in attracting youngsters.

Sohan (2006) highlights those children in Israel and the US have similar impacts on family purchase decision-making. Barlovic's (2006) paper wanted to ban advertisements for food items, leading to obesity among children. He also mentioned other factors that also lead to obesity in children. Boden (2006) paper found an intimidating connection between fashion and youth, constructing a particular image of themselves in front of their peers and friends. The paper by Bridges, Evans, and Shoham also suggested similar findings.

Turner (2006) emphasized giving premiums, toys, and gifts to attract children. He also found most of the claims made in food advertisements were fake. Bergadaa (2007) defined four facets on which each marketer must behave: Personal character and morality, professional know-how, their role in the company and company's ethics, social role, and their decision-making responsibility. The paper questioned the morality of marketers when marketing to children.

Ekstrom (2007) lays the importance of being up-to-date with the children. The significant findings were that schools play an essential role in transferring knowledge from children to parents. Patrick D (2007) proves similar characteristics and influences of Chinese and American children over their parents. According to the findings of Malene (2007), parents feel that children have a modest impact on decision-making. Adults think they have a significant effect on the world, but children believe in the reverse. Families feel they have the final word, but they examine children's behaviour and prior experiences when making decisions that consider their experiences. Children may have a significant impact in various ways, including directly or indirectly, intentionally or subconsciously, and using a variety of approaches.

Brady's (2008) study found web-based food, drink, and candy marketing are viral among kids. Word-of-mouth and web marketing heavily impact children's dietary intake. The study also suggested that TV viewing time has also drastically decreased since children started surfing online. Bujizen's (2008) study goals were to determine the development of purchase-related

parent-child communication (i.e., children's purchase influence attempts, their coercive behaviour, and parent-initiated communication) and the relationship between parent-initiated communication and the development of purchase-related parent-child communication. Buckleitner (2008) provided insight that children had started watching online content at the age of two. Most of the content viewed is commercial rather than informational.

Mittal (2000) proposed that a child's behaviour is molded by watching TV for long hours. Cook (2009) researched from 1939 and proved a rise in studies on children as consumers by many practitioners, academicians, and marketers. Nash (2009) focused on the parent-child purchase relationship. Due to the increased media usage, children are becoming the focal point of any purchase decision made for the whole family. Finally, Roberto (2010) examined the role of licensed cartoon characters appearing on food packaging influencing kids' preferences.

Gaming, Gadgets, and Guilt 2011-2015

This particular era saw the rise of engagement with the Internet amongst children. TV still has a solid presence as a medium of communication. They are engaged in creating virtual avatars, profiles and playing games with friends online. Gadgets connected to the internet like iPads and smartphones were introduced to the lives of preschoolers who started listening to lullabies from online video libraries instead than from their grandparents. Many young children are entering formal schools with extensive contact with computers and the internet. They demonstrate developing navigation, retrieval, and retrieval skills and producing content. (Hopkins et al, 2013; Edward-Groves & Langley, 2009; Siibak & Vinter, 2010; Zevenbergen & Logan, 2008). Many authors have also raised issues with the safety and security of children on the internet. Many studies also undertook parents' perspective of how technology is now an integral part of their children's lives.

Shim (2011) investigated a child's perspective on online advertising. The study found that the child's cognitive development and social learning were crucial antecedents to the child's responses to online advertising. Powell (2011) shows that children below the age of 8 pressure their parents more than those above this age group because they are more mature, understanding, and well-informed about their surroundings. Lawlor (2011) suggested that children have become smarter with passing time and have unlimited access to knowledge through the internet. As a result, they are more knowledgeable at times and actively participate in decisions related to family purchases.

Lingstone (2012) investigated children's use of the internet on two levels, i.e., are demographic and psychological, and second, taking the country as a unit for a comparative perspective.

Akhter (2012) found that parents often accept the pestering power influences of their children when they see that the kids are more aware and informed than they are. It was more about the positive aspects of pester power. Choudhary (2012) identified product categories where pester power is more influential. This paper also highlighted that with age, the tactics of influence pester power changes. Choudhary M. (2012) found that children use many tactics to influence their parents. Demographic factors played a significant role in developing such tactics.

Ironic (2012) examined children's reactions to retail establishments. It was discovered that youngsters were drawn to promotional information in stores and pestered their parents to purchase a specific product. Nash (2012) demonstrated that parent-child relationships are the primary participants in the "game" of pester power. However, the article indicated that pester power has no detrimental influence when it comes to parent-child purchase interaction.

Gulla A. (2013) concluded that the impact of TV commercials on children's pester power enhances their influence on their parents' purchasing behaviour. Shen (2013) used self-determination theory to understand the motives behind children's use of the internet. Oprea

(2013) researched the long-term influence of commercials on children's consumerism. Brennan (2014) discovered several characteristics that aid in developing brand attitudes and behaviours in children aged 7 to 12. The most dominant agents were found to be socialising agents. Sundar (2014) investigated if an entertainment area aids in producing pester power to attract children and their families to fast food restaurants. Children have a significant voice in family dining out selections and are also highly brand loyal.

Ozel (2015) investigated how the tourist sector now focuses on children by providing kids play areas, customised kids' meals, and dedicated kid beds in hotels. Taghavi (2015) observed that packaging and brand have a crucial impact on the purchasing decisions of Iranian children and parents. Spotwood (2015) discovered that children are extremely vulnerable to TV advertisements and that parents, due to their hectic lifestyles, are powerless to make their children aware of the adverse effects of such advertisements.

Naredla (2015) discovered that youngsters readily express their food and toy preferences and influence their parents' selections. The report also found that youngsters have become significantly more educated about market trends due to media exposure. U. Lenka (2015) created a theoretical framework that expresses the critical role that socialisation agents play in growing consumerism among youngsters.

Pestering, Pressure, and Parenting 2016-2021

The researches highlighted the parenting pressure parents are facing at present. This era has seen many evolving changes in parenting communication patterns. Parents have started accepting advice from their offspring. Parents' self-efficacy, sharenting, tiger parenting, digital literacy of the family, influencer marketing, generation alpha, positive pester power, and ethics of marketing to children, are the latest concepts taking shape in many pieces of research.

Divakar (2016) researched to understand the TV viewing behaviour among children living in urban and rural parts of Goa. This research established that children in rural areas spend more time viewing advertisements than their counterparts in urban areas.

Singh (2016) highlighted different effects of the relationship youngsters have with buying behaviour and e-retailers. The impact of socializing agents has emerged as an essential factor in the growth of consumerism in India. Fabrizio (2016) found that if young children know which food chains offer collectables or premiums, their discussions with their parents about where to eat during an outing are apparent.

Winkler (2016) proposed that if healthy food items like organic fruits and vegetables and low-sugar substitutes are placed in supermarkets instead of high sugar and high-fat content products, consumers will give positive feedback, which will be a win-win situation for both marketers and consumers. P. Anitha (2016) suggested that children's pestering varies differently in different types of family communication, which shapes the final result. A conceptual framework was established. Limaye (2017) looked at the ethical issues of using children in marketing promotions by commercial organizations.

Alhuwalia (2017) found that working mothers are more liberal towards the undue demands of children. Whereas the homemakers were more inclined towards healthy lifestyles for children. Both the mothers find advertisements informative and impactful. Naumovska (2017) found that regardless of the age of children and teens, they are all overexposed to digital gadgets and social media. The paper proposed a model that, if followed, could benefit both parents and marketers. Dikcius (2017) aimed to classify the instruments used to measure children's engagement in parental purchase decisions and to develop a typology of these instruments. Burroughs (2017) investigated the growing relationship between media viewing patterns and

the lives of young children. It was in special reference to the development of the YouTube Kids App.

Bill (2018) found that in most households whenever parents shop for groceries they are accompanied by their children. It also highlighted that parent shop more when children attend them. Folkvord (2019) studied the time children spend watching Vloggers, whether they see the product placements in the vlogs, and how children get influenced and pester parents to buy the products. Finally, Langert (2019) identified McDonald's Happy Meal as one of the significant factors making 2 out of every 3 Americans falls into the category of obese. This article shows how McDonald's tried to give a much healthier option to the consumers, but it all failed in front of the fries.

Askelson (2019) studied the child's perspective on pester power when demanding fruits and vegetables. Findings suggest that when kids require fruits and veggies, parents fulfil just one request. The focus groups provided sufficient evidence that kids use pester power to influence parents' decisions. Bill (2019) suggested that parents act as gatekeepers when the child demands unhealthy products. Still, they are reluctant to express the same power in malls and shops as they are afraid of the disruptive behaviour the child might show. The paper used the Eyberg Child Behaviour Inventory to understand pester power during shopping trips and grocery stores.

Cristian (2019) aimed to understand the child's perspective of Pester Power. It was a focused group study where children were involved with drawings and role-playing activities while their responses were recorded for further studies. Maree (2019) questioned the ethic of the marketers who showcase collectables as social currency in a child's world. The advertising appeals to greed to collect all the collectables before time runs out. Kaur (2019) showed that mothers were

concerned about unhealthy eating. Advertisements were the most prominent tool to pass on information regarding the new offers in the market.

Dikcius (2019) focused on providing clarity on the following concepts. First, it focuses on the theoretical and methodological contrast between the ideas of kid involvement in the family-buying process and child influence. Second, Warren (2019) highlighted how styles of parenting influence mediation behaviour. Third, it was also found that parental stress was also a stronger predictor of parental mediation.

Singh (2020) found that exposure to the media has made children educate their parents about environmental concerns and sustainability. Key findings suggested that when children became environment-sensitive even parents started to react accordingly. Finally, Andrei (2020) provided an in-depth analysis of Nestlé's Healthy Kid Programme among schoolchildren in India. The campaign's main focus was to promote nutrition and a healthy lifestyle for children and build a brand's positive image in children's minds.

Dikcius (2020) clarified the concept of participation and influence of children over parental purchase decisions. The paper developed a scale to measure the degree of influence in various products used by children. Kuttimani (2020) highlights a subscription box called "Flintobox" for children, newly launched in the Indian market through multi-channel digital marketing. They showed ads of children using the box and having hours of fun without TV and mobile phones. This created a massive buzz about Flintobox amongst educated parents and children.

Naumovska (2020) focused on the level of digital literacy of parents who can educate their children about the online hazards, illusions, persuasions, and unhealthy overexposure of digital content. The paper also highlights that it's a shared responsibility of parents, schools, advertisers, and institutions to protect children from harmful advertisement practices. Finally,

Chellasamy (2020) showed a positive correlation between antecedents of consumer socializing through media in adolescents on family decision making.

Shoshani (2021) revealed that positive affect, self-efficacy, satisfaction, and better subjective well-being were positively connected to parents' flow experiences during interactions with their children. Khademi (2021) showed that children's emotions significantly influence their buying loyalty, with the more favourable feelings they have about a product, the more loyal they are. It is discovered that these maverick customers make purchasing decisions irrespective of their parents' communication approaches, indicating that family communication patterns have a moderating effect.

Bibliometric Analysis

According to Berger and Baker (2014), bibliometric analysis is a unique tool for evaluating and assessing the effectiveness of published research efforts within a field. Citation analysis is one of the most commonly used methods within the bibliometric analysis. The second goal of this study has been accomplished by the analysis given in this part. It displays the citation information of significant research publications and the journals referenced in this domain, along with author-indexed keywords, country-wise citation details, and author impact analysis.

Citation counts of any research article are an objective method of determining the effect and worth of any given publication in the research area. As a result, it was utilized in this study to identify the most important works from the numerous publications referenced. **Figure 1** illustrates the steps of literature collection and selection. The Scopus database was selected as the data collection source in this study. There are two explanations for this. For starters, the Scopus database is the most comprehensive interdisciplinary collection of peer-reviewed publications in social scientific research (Norris and Oppenheim 2007). Second, it gives a variety of data forms that may be processed further in bibliometric software.

The keywords for the search were "children," "influence," "purchase decisions," and "households" were included and were connected by the Boolean logic gate "AND" with the keywords as mentioned earlier. Furthermore, the period was set from 2001 to 2021. Based on these criteria, 226 articles were collected in this initial search and were saved in CSV format as per the VOSviewer requirement.

The original 226 articles in **figure 1** were reduced to 108 quality papers for bibliometric analysis. The inclusion criteria for the study were that the publications were relevant to parents and children's purchasing decisions. Articles written in English were considered. To exclude irrelevant studies, the remaining papers were restricted to the following topic areas that may be connected to children's influence: social science, business, management, and accounting, computer science, arts and humanities, psychology, and economics, econometrics, and finance.

Figure 2 depicts the rapid increase in publications relating to children's effect on purchasing decisions throughout time. Analyzing **Figure 2**, it is noteworthy that the number of published publications was less than ten until 2015. There is a fast shift in numbers during the years 2018 and after. It demonstrates the researchers' interest in this specific subject. Despite the domain's presence in every region of the world, only a few have been discovered. As a result, we can safely infer that research on children's influence is still in its early stages and will likely gain more attention in the future years as the marketing technique expands.

Table 1 lists the top ten journals where the papers were published. The number of citations and articles obtained from these journals is also included in the table. This research has received the most reports and sources from young consumers. **Figure 3** shows a positive and robust link where similar keywords indexed by authors appear together in these journals.

Authored Keyword Time Lapse

Figure 4 depicts the use of authored keywords from 2001 to 2021 with the help of the color scheme "Blue to Yellow." Part one of the paper, which is a literature review, highlights the important words used in different timelines.

Author impact analysis

This section contains information on the top ten most influential writers, whose works have been widely referenced by other academics. The ranking is based on the number of citations per author each year. The rationale for discovering citations per author each year is that a single author has authored a few articles, others by two authors, and others by more than two authors. Similarly, the years in which certain publications were published significantly varied. As a result, ranking on this basis becomes more critical.

Table 2 provides information on the number of research articles published by the specific author on this topic between 2001 and 2021. **Figure 5** depicts the same authors with prominent nodes with great strengths between the citations mentioned in Table 2.

Author-Indexed Keywords

Figure 6 displays the keywords indexed by the writers of the publications. A total of 315 words are divided into 16 clusters, as shown in **figure 6**. The graph also shows a broad view of developments from 2001 to 2021. The colour scheme with the time frame bar aids comprehension. Not only is the time range highlighted, but so are the keywords that were utilized more frequently in many study publications than others. The noteworthy keywords in the analysis are "Child", "Decision Making", "Human", "Parents", "Consumer Attitude", "Purchasing", "Purchase Decisions", "Children", "Retailing", "Super Market", "Consumer Research", "Marketing", "Consumer Attitude". Detail about top 40 Keywords with Occurrence and link strength I given in **Table 3**.

Countries-Wise Distribution of citation

To gain an overview of the literature, it is important to comprehend the citations of these publications on a country-by-country basis. The United States has the most citations on the list. Although India and the United Kingdom have comparable citations, the UK's link strength is more robust than India's. This pattern shows that research on this topic is presently persuading in these locations. Table 4 lists nations that had at least three citations.

Conclusion and Suggestions for Future Research

There has been a paradigm shift in marketing communication from 2001 to 2021. Traditional methods of advertising to children are now replaced by influential marketing through social media channels. Moreover, marketing is now no more limited to a geographical boundary. Since screen time is reaching newer heights every day post-COVID-19, trends of children influencing their parents' purchase decision-making are observed strongly.

Due to the broader scope and extensive coverage, the meta-synthesis of existing studies to identify future research directions is extremely significant. However, existing literature assessments are primarily descriptive, and the underlying conceptual and intellectual structure is unexplored. The current study aims to address this research gap.

To carry out the study, a scientifically validated literature review approach was given by Yuetian Yu (2020). Journals, papers, authors, and keywords were among the scientific actors employed in the analysis. Furthermore, quantitative indicators such as frequency of publication and qualitative measures such as the citation index are utilized for performance evaluation. Finally, co-occurrence and co-citation analyses assisted in comprehending current literature's conceptual and intellectual structure to identify new study areas.

Few Asian studies are concentrating on a new generation of parents that participate in a different type of parenting known as 'tiger parenting,' a term created by Prof. Amy Chua of Yale Law School in 2011. There is no question that today's youngsters are more independent and freer to express themselves. One of the primary causes of this is tiger parenting. In the majority of metropolitan households nowadays, both parents work. Parents want their children to be successful academically and in extracurricular activities, as well as to be self-sufficient in deciding what is best for them. This area may be researched further in terms of children's influence on families.

From the above literature review and bibliometric analysis, it is evident that most of the studies were done in developed countries like the USA, UK, Brazil, and Australia. Therefore, to understand the influence of children on purchase decisions in households in India, it is necessary to understand this domain in the present context.

The representation of masculinity and femininity in advertising is also a critical topic that has been loosely explored in the past, as advertising is not only a source of sales but also a source of knowledge. It has been discovered that some children's advertisements are often guided by gender stereotyping through the usage of colours and characters in the adverts.

Today, decisions related to purchasing in a family household are interactive, and children actively participate in purchase decisions. However, even though very few studies are available that establish links between a child's cognitive and demographic characteristics, the demographic factors of their parents, and the child's effect on family purchase decision-making, additional prospective studies are needed to evaluate this direction.

In developing countries, there are many misconceptions that families are run and governed by the figureheads or the breadwinners, but indeed, with time, extravagant makeshifts are happening. This is because modern parents accept their children's requests and alter the whole

buying decision-making process. Therefore, it is necessary to comprehend these parents' self-efficacy related to their parenting quality and children's involvement.

Further studies are needed to examine parents' willingness to accept the child's influence. Most of the literature places pester power as the only factor of influence. Reasons for parents' willingness and acceptance need proper interpretation.

As pester power is booming day by day, children are now becoming more materialistic. This has led to increasing consumerism amongst children. Hence, there is a need to study the factors that add up to this. The majority of the studies mentioned the impact of children on one or more product categories. However, no thorough research identifies significant product categories and the degree of child impact on each of them.

Furthermore, research may be conducted to determine the digital literacy levels of parents to correlate it with their children's use of the internet and social media. There is a scarcity of data to assess the moderating effects of gender-based marketing techniques and their effects on children's purchasing patterns. It may be used to create theoretical models for future study.

This paper provides a necessary theoretical addition to the domain of consumer behavior analytics, particularly in connection to the buying decisions of children and parents. This study offered a review of the literature and provided an in-depth content analysis of emerging themes for identification. This study not only offered a review of the literature but also provided an in-depth content analysis of emerging topics to identify future research directions. The systematic depiction of findings will assist practitioners in maximizing the potential of this domain.

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Figure 1: The steps of literature collection and selection

Figure 2 The number of publications on children's influence on purchase decisions over the years.

Nanda D., Hu C., Bai B.	2006	Journal of Travel and Tourism Marketing	54
Correa T., Fierro C., Reyes M., Dillman	2019	International Journal of Behavioural Nutrition and Physical Activity	49

Source: Scopus

Table 2 Top 10 Prominent Authors with Citation

Figure-5 Author impact analysis

Keyword	Occurrences	Total link strength	Keyword	Occurrences	Total link strength
child	14	400	child nutrition	4	132
human	13	398	controlled study	4	122
decision making	18	393	focus groups	4	116

female	12	377	adolescent	4	111
humans	11	358	parents	7	109
male	11	335	food packaging	4	108
article	9	284	information processing	3	108
food preference	8	275	household	3	104
adult	8	247	marketing	4	104
food preferences	7	241	qualitative research	3	100
choice behaviour	7	233	child behaviour	3	93
consumer attitude	6	199	catering service	3	91
consumer behaviour	6	183	priority journal	3	89
child, preschool	5	169	purchasing	3	88
preschool child	5	169	cost	2	84
psychology	6	158	healthy diet	2	84
economics	5	138	fast food	2	78
child parent relation	4	135	fast foods	2	78
human experiment	4	133	money	2	78

Table-3 Keywords Occurrence and Link Strength

Table 4: Country-Wise Distribution of Citations

Figure-7: Country-Wise Citation Distribution

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